

Styryl hemicyanine dyes with benzo[*d*]thiazolium and substituted *N*-phenylpiperazine end groups binding biological macromolecules

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Abstract

The potential of a series of styryl hemicyanine dyes as fluorescent bioprobes for biologically relevant macromolecules was investigated. The photophysical properties of the dyes were evaluated in the presence of nucleic acids, polysaccharides, and proteins. Pronounced fluorescence enhancement was observed upon interaction with human serum albumin (HSA), β -cyclodextrin polymer (β -CDP), and lipopolysaccharide (LPS), with emission intensities increasing by up to 130-fold relative to the free dyes in solution. The observed fluorescence turn-on effect is attributed to restricted intramolecular rotation and stabilization of the locally excited state upon binding within hydrophobic or supramolecular environments. Geometry optimization at the M06-2X level and molecular docking studies were performed to elucidate the binding modes and revealed the key contribution of hydrophobic, electrostatic, and host–guest interactions to complex formation.

Keywords

Styryl hemicyanine dyes, fluorescence, biological macromolecules, molecular docking, DFT

Introduction

Fluorescent labeling has proven itself as an indispensable tool in contemporary molecular biology, enabling precise visualization and quantification of biologically significant macromolecules (Tyagi and Kramer 1996; Li et al. 2017; Kozma and Kele 2019; Reja et al. 2021). This technique

involves the covalent (Forsythe et al. 2006; Díaz-García and Badía-Laiño 2019) or non-covalent (Kricka and Fortina 2009; Kurutos et al. 2018) attachment of fluorophores to macromolecules, for example, nucleic acids, proteins, and carbohydrates, allowing their behavior, interactions, and spatial distribution to be studied with unparalleled accuracy and specificity (Yano 2019). The development of

advanced fluorophores, combined with sophisticated imaging techniques, has facilitated breakthroughs in fields ranging from cell biology to drug discovery (Gao et al. 2019; Cambré and Aertsen 2020; Nikitaki et al. 2020; Bajaj et al. 2021; Guillou et al. 2022; Suyama et al. 2023). The importance of fluorescent labeling lies in its ability to illuminate molecular processes in real time under physiological conditions, offering insights into dynamic cellular processes such as signal transduction, gene expression, and protein trafficking (Wombacher and Cornish 2011; Sheng et al. 2020; Eustáquio et al. 2024). Moreover, innovations in fluorescent labeling strategies, including site-specific tagging and genetically encoded fluorophores, have expanded the scope of applications, allowing researchers to study complex biological systems with high resolution and minimal perturbation. For instance, functionalization of fluorescent dyes with cucurbit[8]uril allows the monitoring of enzyme activity, thus providing high sensitivity and versatility to the process of inhibitor screening (Biedermann et al. 2015; Alzard et al. 2019; Jia et al. 2019). Fluorescent labeling has also been used to easily identify and monitor biological markers such as human serum albumin (HSA). HSA is a biomarker for various pathological conditions, including renal and liver diseases. Early diagnostics of such conditions relies on the selective and sensitive detection of HSA in different biological samples (Lee et al. 2019; Lü et al. 2019; Wang et al. 2020; Hu et al. 2021; Liu et al. 2023; Xiao et al. 2023; Wang et al. 2024; Chinnappan et al. 2025). The ability to monitor biomacromolecules in real time with this approach has found applications in fundamental research areas as well. Using fluorescent biomarkers to label human lipopolysaccharides (LPS) has allowed the visualization and localization of LPS within living cells, which is important to understand how LPS interact with different tissues and cells, with particular emphasis on understanding immune responses and inflammation, thus allowing early diagnosis and monitoring of conditions such as sepsis (Voss et al. 2007; Duheron et al. 2014; Zhang et al. 2017; Liu et al. 2018). In a similar manner, the labeling of β -cyclodextrin polymers (β -CDP) has proven crucial for studying their endocytosis and intracellular transport and providing insights into their mechanisms of action and potential therapeutic applications (Plazzo et al. 2012; Réti-Nagy et al. 2015).

The earliest reports in the literature concerning styryl cyanine dyes can be found as early as 1920 (Barbier 1920; König and Treichel 1921; Mills and Pope 1922) and were first used as sensitizers for photographic plates (Mills and Pope 1922). Their successful application in this field led to their rapid development as a subclass for more than 60 years. Systematic studies demonstrated the ability of styryl dyes to also be used as fluorogenic markers for binding biopolymers such as DNA, RNA, and proteins (Ephardt and Fromherz 1989; Kovalska et al. 2005; Kovalska et al. 2006; Balanda et al. 2007; Volkova et al. 2007; Shindy 2017). Recently, the capacity of styryl dyes as theragnostic agents was successfully demonstrated as well (Wang and Jiang 2019). Previous work in

the area of biolabeling led to the identification of styryl hemicyanine dyes consisting of benzothiazole and *N*-methylpiperazine or *N*-phenylpiperazine scaffolds with excellent binding affinities for different ds-polynucleotides and G-quadruplexes (Zonjić et al. 2022). The substitution of the piperazine unit with a methyl or phenyl group strongly influenced the dyes' binding modes, binding affinities, spectroscopic responses, and antiproliferative activities (Zonjić et al. 2022). Compounds with *N*-methylpiperazine substituents showed a significant preference for AT-DNA polynucleotides and demonstrated AT-minor groove binding, which manifested in a strong fluorescence increase, significant double-helix stabilization, and positive induced circular dichroism spectra (Zonjić et al. 2022).

Recently, a series of novel styryl hemicyanine dyes containing substituents at different positions in the *N*-phenylpiperazine fragment were synthesized in the laboratory (Aleksandrova et al. 2025). The aim of the present study is to describe and investigate the photophysical properties of these dyes and their interactions with various oligomers and macromolecules. The obtained results provide insight into the structure–property relationships governing their behavior and further highlight the potential of these dyes for biological and bioanalytical applications.

Materials and methods

Chemicals and reagents

The styryl hemicyanine dyes were previously synthesized in the laboratory through Knoevenagel condensation in the presence of a sterically hindered base (Aleksandrova et al. 2025). The nucleic acids (DNA and RNA); biological oligomers; and macromolecules—cucurbit[8]uril (CB8), calix[8]arene (C8A), human serum albumin (HSA), lipopolysaccharide (LPS) from *Escherichia coli*, β -cyclodextrin polymer (β -CDP), and γ -cyclodextrin (γ -CD)—were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO), the buffer solution Tris hydrochloride (Tris-HCl), and ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (EDTA) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich.

Spectral studies

UV-Vis spectra were measured on a Shimadzu UV-1800 spectrophotometer, and the fluorescence spectra were obtained on a PerkinElmer LS45 fluorescence spectrophotometer (slit widths were 5 nm).

Preparation of working solutions

The stock solutions of the dyes were prepared in DMSO at a concentration of 2×10^{-3} M. The dye concentration in the working solutions was 2×10^5 M for the absorption measurements and 2×10^{-6} M for the fluorescence measurements. The DNA and RNA were prepared in

Scheme 1. Structures of monocationic styryl dyes bearing substituted *N*-phenylpiperazine end groups.

Tris-EDTA buffer solution (pH = 7.5) at a concentration of 1 mg/mL. The biological oligomers and macromolecules were prepared in Tris-HCl buffer solution at a concentration of 1 mg/mL.

Computational details

For the docking analysis, AutoDock Vina 1.1.2 (Trott and Olson 2010). The determination of the grid box size and the preparation of the PDBQT files of the ligands and receptors were carried out using AutoDock Tools (ADT) version 1.5.6. To prepare the receptors for docking, the non-standard heteroatoms, including water molecules, crystallization ligands, and additional ions, were removed, and only the primary macromolecular structure was retained. Thereafter, polar hydrogens and Kollman charges were added. The docking results were visualized using the PyMOL molecular graphic system. The crystallographic structures of the receptors were obtained from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) with the following codes: HSA (site I, PDB ID: 2BXP; site II, PDB ID: 2XWO), β -cyclodextrin (PDB ID: 5YN7), and LPS (PDB ID: 1F11). Each predicted binding pose (conformation) of the ligands was evaluated by a docking score, which represents the estimated binding free energy (ΔG) in kcal/mol.

Quantum chemical computations were performed to investigate the geometry, electronic structure, and spectral properties of the studied dyes. Geometry optimizations and photophysical property calculations for both monomeric and 1:1 host-guest inclusion complexes formed with β -cyclodextrin were carried out using the Gaussian 16 software package (Frisch et al. 2016). All structures were fully optimized at the density functional theory (DFT) level using the M06-2X/6-31G(d,p) method (Zhao and Truhlar 2008). To reproduce the experimental conditions, all calculations were performed in a water medium corresponding to TE buffer conditions. Solvent effects were modeled using the SMD continuum solvation formalism in Gaussian 16 (Marenich et al. 2009). The stability of the optimized complexes was evaluated through the complexation Gibbs free energy ($\Delta G_{\text{complexation}}$), where more negative values correspond to thermodynamically more favorable complex formation. The complexation free energies were calculated according to Eq. (1):

$$\Delta G_{\text{complexation}} = G_{\text{complex (dye@CD)}} - (G_{\text{dye}} + G_{\text{BCD}}) \quad (1)$$

where $\Delta G_{\text{complexation}}$ represents the Gibbs free energy change associated with complex formation, whereas $G_{\text{complex (dye@CD)}}$, G_{dye} and G_{BCD} represent the Gibbs free energies of the optimized inclusion complex, the isolated dye molecule (guest), and the isolated β -cyclodextrin host, respectively. The electronic absorption properties of the studied dyes and host-guest complexes in water were simulated using TDDFT calculations employing the PBE0 hybrid functional and the 6-31+G(d,p) basis set.

Results

A series of three styryl hemicyanine dyes **4a–4c** (Scheme 1) was previously synthesized in the laboratory via an improved synthetic strategy, utilizing a sterically hindered base and a minimal amount of solvent (Aleksandrova et al. 2025). This approach resulted in high-purity products with yields exceeding 70%.

Photophysical properties of dyes in the presence of biological macromolecules

The photophysical properties of compounds **4a–4c** in buffer and in the presence of macromolecules were studied, and their spectral characteristics are summarized in Tables 1, 2. The dyes show absorption maxima λ_{abs} in the range 457–462 nm, and their emission maxima λ_{em} are bathochromically shifted to 584–591 nm. All three dyes exhibit weak fluorescence in solution that changes upon interaction with biological macromolecules. The photophysical behavior of dyes **4a–4c** is presented in Fig. 1. A significant change in the fluorescence intensity is observed for compounds **4a** (Fig. 1A) and **4b** (Fig. 1B) in the presence of HSA and β -CDP. An extremely high increase in the fluorescence of dyes **4a** and **4b** was observed in the presence of LPS from *Escherichia coli* (Fig. 1A, B). The fluorescence intensity, expressed as the ratio of the fluorescence of the dye-macromolecule complex (F) to that of the dye in TE buffer (F_0), is illustrated in Fig. 2. Dye **4a** shows the most pronounced fluorescence enhancement upon binding to lipopolysaccharide (LPS) from *Escherichia coli* and a moderate fluorescence increase upon binding to human serum albumin (HSA) and β -cyclodextrin polymer. Notably, exclusive fluorescence enhancement exceeding 100-fold is observed in the presence of LPS from

Table 1. Spectral characteristics of styryl hemicyanine dyes **4a–4c** in buffer solution and their UV-Vis absorption maxima in the presence of NA, cucurbit[8]uril (CB8), calix[8]arene (C8A), human serum albumin (HSA), lipopolysaccharide (LPS), β -cyclodextrin polymer (β -CDP), and γ -cyclodextrin (γ -CD).

Entry	Free dye ^a	RNA ^b	DNA ^b	CB8 ^b	β -CDP ^b	C8A ^b	γ -CD ^b	HSA ^b	LPS ^b
	λ_{abs}	λ_{abs}	λ_{abs}	λ_{abs}	λ_{abs}	λ_{abs}	λ_{abs}	λ_{abs}	λ_{abs}
4a	449	505	509	485	476	480	490	494	495
4b	460	502	505	486	475	491	460	480	493
4c	460	508	500	480	475	493	465	480	480

^a λ_{abs} (nm): maximum wavelengths of absorption spectra; dye concentration $c = 2 \times 10^{-5}$ M in TE buffer;

^b λ_{abs} (nm): maximum wavelengths of absorption spectra of the dyes in the presence of macromolecules; the concentration of the nucleic acids, biological saccharides, and proteins was 1 mg/mL; dye concentration $c = 2 \times 10^{-5}$ M.

Table 2. Fluorescence maxima and intensities of styryl hemicyanine dyes **4a–4c** in the presence of NA, cucurbit[8]uril (CB8), calix[8]arene (C8A), human serum albumin (HSA), lipopolysaccharide (LPS), β -cyclodextrin polymer (β -CDP), and γ -cyclodextrin (γ -CD).

Entry	Free dye ^a		RNA			DNA			CB8			β -CDP		
	λ_{ex}	λ_{em}	λ_{ex}	λ_{em}	F/F ⁰									
4a	450	585	455	591	2.0	455	586	2.3	485	580	7.2	475	581	77.9
4b	460	589	480	594	6.3	480	593	5.7	490	589	3.1	475	574	33.4
4c	460	586	510	584	8.8	500	580	3.9	480	578	2.0	480	575	4.2
Entry	Free dye ^a		γ -CD			HSA			LPS			C8A		
	λ_{ex}	λ_{em}	λ_{ex}	λ_{em}	F/F ⁰									
4a	450	585	472	592	1.7	495	578	54.8	500	589	126	480	594	2.8
4b	460	589	470	588	1.9	480	581	35.2	490	588	51.1	490	596	1.6
4c	460	586	465	581	1.6	480	577	4.3	480	580	11.2	470	602	1.9

λ_{em} (nm): maximum wavelengths of emission spectra of the dyes in the presence of macromolecules; the concentration of the nucleic acids, biological saccharides, and proteins was 1 mg/mL; dye concentration $c = 2 \times 10^{-6}$ M in TE buffer.

Escherichia coli (Fig. 2A). In contrast, compound **4c** exhibits the smallest change in fluorescence after binding to the studied biomolecules (Fig. 1C).

Molecular docking

To explore the preferred modes of interaction of dyes **4a–4c** with LPS, HSA, and β -cyclodextrin (β -CDP), molecular docking studies were performed. The interaction energies of the dyes with the biomolecule models are summarized in Supplementary material 1: tables S1–S3. Multiple binding conformations were evaluated, and only the most energetically favorable ones are discussed. The docking scores obtained by AutoDock were used to grade the conformations in the order of their ΔG values in kcal/mol. Docking studies with human serum albumin (HSA) were carried out using two crystallographic structures corresponding to binding site I (PDB ID: 2BXP) and binding site II (PDB ID: 2XWO). The binding site I pocket combines a hydrophobic interior with a polar entrance, enabling the binding of bulky heterocyclic drugs (Lexa et al. 2014). The binding energies at sites I and II differ by approximately 1 kcal/mol (Supplementary material 1: figs S1, S2). Trp214 is the hallmark residue of site I. The dyes form π - π interactions with Trp214, whereas the phenyl moiety of the dye is accommodated within a hydrophobic pocket of HSA (surface representation is shown in Fig. 3). In this region, it engages in hydrophobic contacts with residues Phe206, Ala210, Phe211, Leu347,

Leu481, and Val482. The hydrophobic interactions and the π - π interactions predominate.

The investigated styryl dyes **4a–4c** interact with lipopolysaccharide (LPS) predominantly through hydrophobic interactions, as illustrated by the surface representation in Fig. 4.

The docking analysis further demonstrates that styryl dyes **4a** and **4b** interact with β -cyclodextrin via hydrophobic inclusion within the cyclodextrin cavity (Fig. 5). In contrast, no energetically favorable binding conformation was identified for dye **4c**. The docking approach predicted unrealistically high binding energies for the interaction with β -cyclodextrin; therefore, DFT calculations were employed to obtain a more reliable description of the host-guest complexes.

Quantum chemical computations

Quantum chemical computations were performed to investigate the geometry, electronic structure, and spectral properties of the studied dye- β -cyclodextrin complexes (Figs 6, 7). The formation of 1:1 host-guest complexes with β -CDP was further investigated by DFT calculations. Different orientations of the dye molecule inside the cavity were studied (Fig. 6). In the **4a**- β -CDP complex 1, the *N*-phenylpiperazine moiety is oriented toward the narrow rim of the β -cyclodextrin cavity, whereas in the **4a**- β -CDP complex 2, the benzothiazole heterocycle is inserted through the same opening (Fig. 6). The Gibbs free energy of complex formation was calculated to be -21.9 kcal/mol

A. 4a

B. 4b

C. 4c

Figure 1. Emission spectra of dye: **A. 4a**; **B. 4b**; **C. 4c** ($c = 2 \times 10^{-6}$ M) in the presence of TE and Tris-HCl buffers (pH = 7.5) and NA, cucurbit[8]uril, calix[8]arene, HSA, LPS, β -CDP, and γ -CD ($c = 1$ mg/mL).

for **4a**- β -CDP complex 1 and -13.0 kcal/mol for **4a**- β -CDP complex 2, indicating spontaneous formation and high thermodynamic stability in both cases.

A. 4a

B. 4b

C. 4c

Figure 2. The change in the fluorescence intensity (F/F_0) of the dyes: **A. 4a**; **B. 4b**; **C. 4c** ($c = 2 \times 10^{-6}$ M) in the presence of biological macromolecules ($c = 1$ mg/mL).

The energies and shape representation of the frontier molecular orbitals for the optimized S0-state geometry of the isolated dye and the host-guest complex from TDP-BE0/6-31+G(d,p) computations are shown in Fig. 7.

Figure 3. Docking modes of energy-minimized poses of styryl dyes **4a** (green), **4b** (magenta), and **4c** (cyan) within site I of HSA.

Figure 4. Docking modes of energy-minimized poses of styryl dyes **4a** (magenta), **4b** (cyan), and **4c** (green) with LPS.

Figure 5. Docking modes of energy-minimized poses of styryl dyes **4a** (cyan) and **4b** (green) with β -cyclodextrin. The most stable conformers of complexes of dyes **4a** and **4b** with β -cyclodextrin polymers.

A. **4a**- β -CDP complex 1

B. **4a**- β -CDP complex 2

Figure 6. M06-2X/6-31G(d,p)-optimized stable conformers of the β -cyclodextrin complexes formed by different orientations of dye **4a** toward the narrow rim of the β -CDP cavity.

Discussion

The fluorescence behavior of the dyes was investigated in different microenvironments, revealing pronounced differences depending on the interacting biomolecule. The studied styryl hemicyanine dyes **4a**–**4c** exhibited varying degrees of fluorescence enhancement upon binding to different biological targets. In a previous study, it was demonstrated that these dyes do not display a significant fluorescence response in the presence of double-stranded DNA (dsDNA) due to an efficient photoinduced electron

Figure 7. Energies and shape representation of HOMO and LUMO of isolated **4a** and its inclusion complex in water from M06-2X/6-31+G(d,p) computations.

transfer (PET) process that quenches fluorescence (Aleksandrova et al. 2025). In contrast, substantial fluorescence enhancement was observed herein in the presence of lipopolysaccharide (LPS) isolated from the shell of *Escherichia coli*, human serum albumin (HSA), and β -cyclodextrin polymers (β -CDP), indicating the formation of stable dye–biomolecule complexes (Figs 1, 2). The distinct fluorescence responses observed for DNA and the other investigated biomacromolecules can be attributed to differences in binding modes and microenvironmental effects. Interaction with DNA primarily involves the chromophore system and does not sufficiently perturb the electronic properties of the *N*-phenylpiperazine PET donor. In contrast, binding to HSA, β -cyclodextrin, and especially LPS provides rigid hydrophobic environments and electrostatic stabilization of the protonated donor moiety. These effects reduce the electron-donating ability of the piperazine fragment, suppress the PET process, and consequently lead to pronounced fluorescence enhancement.

The fluorescence increase observed upon interaction with cyclodextrins clearly supports the formation of host–guest inclusion complexes. To elucidate the molecular origin of the enhanced fluorescence in these systems, DFT computations and molecular docking studies were performed to determine the preferred binding modes and the dominant intermolecular interactions.

Lipopolysaccharide (LPS), a bacterial endotoxin associated with severe inflammatory responses and sepsis, represents an important target for the development of sensitive fluorescent probes (Kimoto et al. 2022). Lipopolysaccharides are essential glycolipids forming the outer membrane of *Escherichia coli* and other Gram-negative

bacteria. They protect the bacteria from antibiotics and stimulate severe, acute immune responses, such as fever and inflammation, in humans (Kimoto et al. 2022). The resistance of Gram-negative bacteria to a variety of chemotherapeutics is becoming an increasingly serious problem. Therefore, the development of selective fluorogenic markers for the visualization of such bacteria is of utmost importance. The introduction of functional groups that target the bacterial envelope may provide guidelines for the application of these groups as pharmacophores in the design of new drugs and formulations. The ideal option is the creation of fluorogenic antibiotics that allow visualization of treated microbiological objects. In this regard, compound **4a** is very promising among the investigated systems, and the highest fluorescence enhancement for all dyes was observed in the presence of LPS. Docking analysis revealed that the dyes interact with LPS and HSA predominantly through hydrophobic interactions, which likely restrict intramolecular motions and suppress non-radiative relaxation pathways. Compounds **4a** and **4b**, bearing substituents in the *meta*- and *ortho*-positions, exhibited significantly stronger fluorescence responses than compound **4c**, which contains a substituent in the *para*-position. The increased symmetry of **4c** allows greater conformational flexibility and rotational freedom within the binding site, facilitating non-radiative decay and resulting in lower fluorescence intensity. In contrast, the more sterically demanding and less symmetric structures of **4a** and **4b** enable stronger interactions with hydrophobic regions of the binding site, thereby restricting intramolecular rotation and enhancing fluorescence emission. This behavior is consistent with the restriction of intramolecular motion

(RIM) mechanism reported for related fluorophores (Li et al. 2020, Tang et al. 2023).

A similar trend was observed in the presence of HSA, where compounds **4a** and **4b** again displayed markedly stronger fluorescence enhancement than **4c** (Table 2; Fig. 2A, B). Docking studies indicated that the styryl dyes preferentially bind to site I of HSA, located within the hydrophobic cavity of domain II, with slightly more favorable binding energies compared to site II in domain III. The dyes form π - π interactions with Trp214 and are further stabilized through hydrophobic contacts with neighboring amino acid residues. These interactions create a rigid microenvironment that suppresses intramolecular rotations and enhances fluorescence emission. Similar behavior has been reported for other fluorescent dyes, which bind preferentially to site I of serum albumin and exhibit enhanced near-infrared fluorescence, making them suitable for sensing and bioimaging applications (Jisha et al. 2010). Such fluorescence responses may be exploited in ligand displacement assays to investigate the binding affinities of biologically relevant compounds, including ibuprofen, warfarin, and digitoxin, which are known to interact with different domains of HSA (Ahn et al. 2008). In contrast, compounds such as somapacitan and nirmatrelvir preferentially bind to domain III (Johansson et al. 2020; Abubakar et al. 2024).

The fluorescence response in the presence of cyclodextrins strongly depended on the cavity size and structural compatibility between the host and guest molecules. The cavity diameters of cyclodextrins are approximately 0.57 nm for α -CD, 0.78 nm for β -CDP, 0.95 nm for γ -CD, and 1.3 nm for δ -CD. Compounds **4a** and **4b** exhibited pronounced fluorescence enhancement in the presence of β -cyclodextrin, whereas a substantially weaker response was observed with γ -CD. This suggests that the cavity size of β -CDP provides the most suitable steric fit for the investigated dyes, enabling efficient inclusion within the hydrophobic oligosaccharide cavity and restricting molecular flexibility through host-guest interactions (Enoch and Swaminathan 2007). Because the rigidity of the molecules in molecular docking simulations was not realistic, the flexibility of the complex geometries and the intermolecular interactions of the 1:1 β -CDP/dye complexes were further examined by M06-2X/6-31G(d,p) computations (Figs 6, 7). For β -CDP, the fluorescence increase is consistent with host-guest inclusion complex formation. Cyclodextrin cavities provide a hydrophobic nanoconfined environment that can partially encapsulate the dye, decrease solvent exposure, and restrict bond rotation. In such systems, fluorescence enhancement is commonly associated with reduced conformational freedom and stabilization of the emissive state within the cyclodextrin cavity. The different orientations of the dye within the β -CDP cavity led to significant differences in the complexation free energies. The Gibbs free energy of complex formation was calculated to be -21.9 kcal/mol for the **4a**- β -CDP complex 1 and -13.0 kcal/mol for the **4a**- β -CDP complex 2, indicating spontaneous formation and high thermodynamic sta-

bility in both cases. This suggests that the binding energy for these host-guest complexes is strongly dependent on the small molecule orientation in the cavity. Comparison of the calculated absorption maxima for the free dye and the corresponding inclusion complexes revealed a bathochromic shift upon encapsulation, in agreement with the experimental observations (Supplementary material 1: table S4). Further computational investigations are currently underway to provide a more detailed understanding of these supramolecular interactions.

Overall, the fluorescence behavior of the investigated dyes is governed by the interplay between molecular structure, binding mode, and microenvironmental effects, highlighting their potential as environment-sensitive fluorescent probes for biomolecular recognition and bioanalytical applications. Specifically, the initial studies described so far on the properties of these new compounds show potential for their application exclusively as fluorogenic biomolecular probes for the recognition and visualization of Gram-negative bacteria.

Conclusion

A series of styryl hemicyanine dyes (**4a**-**4c**) was investigated as environment-sensitive fluorescent probes for biologically relevant macromolecules. The dyes exhibited markedly different fluorescence responses depending on the interacting biomolecular target. Although negligible fluorescence enhancement was observed in the presence of double-stranded DNA due to efficient photoinduced electron transfer (PET) quenching, substantial fluorescence turn-on effects were detected upon interaction with lipopolysaccharide (LPS), human serum albumin (HSA), and β -cyclodextrin polymers (β -CDP). Among the investigated systems, LPS from *E. coli* induced the strongest fluorescence enhancement, highlighting the potential of these dyes as sensitive probes for bacterial endotoxins. Molecular docking and DFT calculations revealed that the fluorescence enhancement originates from the formation of stable dye-biomolecule complexes stabilized predominantly through hydrophobic and π - π interactions. In the case of cyclodextrins, the fluorescence response strongly depended on cavity size and structural complementarity, with β -CDP providing the most favorable steric fit for compounds **4a** and **4b**. DFT calculations confirmed the spontaneous formation of stable 1:1 host-guest inclusion complexes and revealed that the complex stability is highly dependent on the orientation of the dye within the cyclodextrin cavity.

The combined experimental and computational results demonstrate that the fluorescence properties of the investigated dyes are governed by the interplay between molecular structure, binding mode, and microenvironmental effects. The ability of these styryl hemicyanine dyes to selectively respond to hydrophobic and supramolecular environments highlights their promise as fluorescent probes for biomolecular recognition, sensing, and bioanalytical applications.

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Additional information

Conflict of interest

The authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

Ethical statements

The authors declared that no clinical trials were used in the present study.

The authors declared that no experiments on humans or human tissues were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no informed consent was obtained from the humans, donors or donors' representatives participating in the study.

The authors declared that no experiments on animals were performed for the present study.

The authors declared that no commercially available immortalised human and animal cell lines were used in the present study.

Artificial Intelligence (AI) use

The authors accept full responsibility for the content of the manuscript, including the disclosure of any use of AI.

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Author contributions

Conceptualization, T.A., D.C., and A.V.; methodology, D.C., and A.V.; validation, D.C., and A.V.; formal analysis, T.A. and A.P.; investigation, T.A., D.C., and A.V.; resources, A.V., and A.P.; data curation, T.A., D.C., and A.V.; writing—original draft preparation, T.A.; writing—review and editing, D.C., A.V., and A.P.; visualization, T.A., A.P., D.C., and A.V.; supervision, D.C., and A.V.; project administration, A.P. and A.V.; funding acquisition, A.P. and A.V.

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Data availability

All of the data that support the findings of this study are available in the main text or Supplementary Information.

Supplementary material 1

Supplementary figures S1–S3, tables S1–S4

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